

PROBE WG2 “Scientific papers on instrument synergy” - Deliverable 2.2

D2.2: Investigate the potential of instrument synergy for the development of higher-level products and best estimates of key ABL parameters.

Project start date	10/2020
Project end date	04/2024

Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.2
Authors	Document preparation conducted by P. Martinet, E. O'Connor and T. Marke Authors (by alphabetical order): C. Acquistapace, E. Batchvarova, A. Bell, D. Gallucci, H. Diemoz, S.E. Gryning, U. Löhnert, M.J. Granados-Munoz, P. Martinet, Ewan J. O'Connor, I. Stachlewska, J-L. Guerrero Rascado, J-F. Ribaud, V-C Pires

1 INTRODUCTION

During the PROBE Cost action, innovative approaches have been developed to take advantage of instrumental synergy to provide with more accurate ABL geophysical products. Synergy between instrument and modeling tools (radiative transfer models, high resolution simulations) have also been exploited to progress in our understanding of ABL physical processes. Network collaboration achieved during the PROBE Cost action led to several publications which are reported in this document. Several Virtual Mobility Grants (VMG) have also contributed to the network cooperation in view of a larger evaluation of the benefit of new instrumental synergy and the development of new products towards several stakeholders. This document gives a synthesis of all the scientific publications and VMGs contributing to deliverable 2.2: Scientific papers on instrument synergy.

2 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Topic : Instrumental synergy combined with radiative transfer model simulations for aerosol heating rate evaluation:

Reference of the publication: Fasano, G., Diémoz, H., Fountoulakis, I. et al., "Vertical profile of the clear-sky aerosol direct radiative effect in an Alpine valley, by the synergy of ground-based measurements and radiative transfer simulations", <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s42865-021-00041-w>, 2021.

Main outcomes: Synergy between ALC, sun photometer, pyranometer, and radiative transfer models allowed to determine the heating rate of aerosols along the vertical profile and reproduce the variations of direct/diffuse solar irradiance at the surface (useful for solar energy applications).

Main Illustration:

Legend: Average daily atmospheric heating rate. The black bars represent the net heating rate due to aerosol in every layer. The profile of the aerosol extinction coefficient (red line) is also shown.

Topic : Instrument synergy for the spatio-temporal discrimination of polarization and molecular, aerosol and cloud scattering:

Reference of the publication: Dongxiang Wang, Iwona S. Stachlewska, Julien Delanoë, Dragos Ene, Xiaoquan Song, and Dirk Schüttemeyer, "Spatio-temporal discrimination of molecular, aerosol and cloud scattering and polarization using a combination of a Raman lidar, Doppler cloud radar and microwave radiometer," Opt. Express **28**, 20117-20134, <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.393625>, 2020.

Main outcomes: A target classification to discriminate molecular, aerosol, and hydrometeor signatures is conducted using instrument synergy. The particle backward scattering ratio and the linear particle depolarization ratio calculated from Raman lidar signals are used together with Doppler cloud radar velocity/reflectivity, and microwave radiometer temperature/humidity information for the separation and to define thresholds.

Main illustration:

Legend: Synergy for molecule, aerosol and cloud identification derived from a combination of EMORAL Raman-polarization lidar, BASTA Doppler cloud radar, and HATPRO-G2 microwave radiometer.

Topic : Combination of passive and active sensors for temperature and humidity profiling:

Reference of the publication: Turner, D. D. and Löhnert, U., “Ground-based temperature and humidity profiling: combining active and passive remote sensors”, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 3033–3048, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-3033-2021>, 2021.

Main outcomes: This paper explores the synergy of combining ground-based infrared spectrometer, microwave radiometer, and Differential Absorption Lidar observations using an optimal-estimation retrieval framework, quantifying the reduction in the uncertainty in the retrieved profiles and the increase in information content.

Main illustration:

Legend: Retrieved profiles of temperature (a) and water vapor (b), with the uncertainties in these profiles (c, d, respectively), for the passive-only retrievals (red, green, blue), AERI-only on 05:07 UTC on 15 May 2017. The water vapor observed by the DIAL and its uncertainty are included in the figure (purple).

Topic : Ship-based cloud and micro rain radar observations of clouds and precipitation:

Reference of the publication: Acquistapace, C., Coulter, R., Crewell, S., Garcia-Benadi, A., Gierens, R. T., Labbri, G., Myagkov, A., Risse, N., and Schween, J. H., “EUREC⁴A’s Maria S. Merian ship-based cloud and micro rain radar observations of clouds and precipitation”, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2021-265>, 2021.

Main outcomes: During the EUREC⁴A field campaign, the research vessel Maria S. Merian probed trade wind cumulus clouds east of Barbados, as well as in the transition region between the trades and the intertropical convergence zone. Continuous observations of cloud and precipitation profiles were collected at a high

temporal/spatial resolution using a W-band radar and micro-rain radar. An active stabilization platform and a ship motion correction algorithm were used to reduce the impact of ship motions on the Doppler observations. In addition, liquid water path from the 89 GHz passive channel was retrieved.

Main illustration:

Legend: Case study with a) Radar reflectivity from W-band radar, b) attenuated reflectivity from MRR-PRO, and c) ship track on top of the corrected reflectance from MODIS Terra, displaying the flower cloud occurring in the area. The blue circle represents the orbit of the HALO aircraft.

Topic : Combination of wind doppler lidar and ceilometer for boundary layer heights in the Arctic:

Reference of the publication: Gryning, S. E., Batchvarova, E., Floors, R., Münkel, C., Sørensen, L. L., & Skov, H., “Observed aerosol-layer depth at Station Nord in the high Arctic”, *International Journal of Climatology*, 43(7), 3247-3263, <https://doi/full/10.1002/joc.8027>, 2023.

This work has been developed thanks to VMG BATCHV-VM-W2-SYN through a collaboration between DTU University of Denmark and the Bulgarian Academic of Science.

Main outcomes: The depth of the aerosol layer at the Villum Research Station at Station Nord in the high Arctic is analysed based on 8 years of observations from a ceilometer and one full year from a wind lidar. The seasonal variation of the depth of the aerosol layer is discussed as well as new methodology to be able to retrieve aerosol depth below 100 m (below the limits of accurate measurements).

Main Illustration:

Legend: Histogram of the depth of the aerosol layer at Station Nord in GreenLand based on attenuated backscatter profiles that are composed of CNR observations between 40 and 100 m from a wind lidar and the ceilometer observations.

Topic : Combination of thermodynamic and microphysical measurements from microwave radiometers for data assimilation experiments:

Reference of the publication: Martinet, P., Unger, V., Burnet, F. *et al.*, “A dataset of temperature, humidity, and liquid water path retrievals from a network of ground-based microwave radiometers dedicated to fog investigation”, *Bull. of Atmos. Sci. & Technol.* **3**, 6, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42865-022-00049-w>, 2022.

Main outcomes: During the SOFOG3D experiment (2019 / 2020), 8 ground-based microwave radiometers from France, Germany and Russia have been deployed to work on fog forecast improvement through data assimilation experiments. This paper presents the data processing and the database available for all users online.

Main Illustration:

Legend: Example of level2 products produced by microwave radiometer for the 25th of December 2019. From top left to bottom right: a) boundary layer temperature profiles, b) composite temperature profile, c) absolute humidity profiles, d) relative humidity profiles, e) integrated water vapor, and f) liquid water path.

Topic : Passive and active sensors synergy for cloud property retrievals:

Reference for the publication: Pîrloagă, Răzvan, Dragoș Ene, Mihai Boldeanu, Bogdan Antonescu, Ewan J. O'Connor, and Sabina Ștefan, "Ground-Based Measurements of Cloud Properties at the Bucharest–Măgurele Cloudnet Station: First Results" *Atmosphere* 13, no. 9: 1445, <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13091445>, 2022.

Main outcomes: A statistical analysis of the synergistic Cloudnet target classification, using Cloud radar, ceilometer, and microwave radiometer, is conducted over a time period of 18 months. Seasonal variability of cloud occurrence and type are presented together with the thermodynamic conditions from a numerical weather prediction model.

Main Illustration:

Legend: Instruments installed at the Măgurele Centre for Atmosphere and Radiation studies (MARS) used in this study: (a) 94 GHz RPG cloud radar, (b) HATPRO radiometer, and (c) CHM15k ceilometer.

Topic : Passive and active sensor synergy for the retrieval of fog microphysical properties:

Reference of the publication: Bell, A., Martinet, P., Caumont, O., Burnet, F., Delanoë, J., Jorquera, S., Seity, Y., and Unger, V., “An optimal estimation algorithm for the retrieval of fog and low cloud thermodynamic and micro-physical properties”, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 15, 5415–5438, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-15-5415-2022>, 2022.

Main outcomes: A newly developed one-dimensional variational (1D-Var) algorithm designed for the retrieval of temperature, specific humidity and liquid water content profiles with both cloud radar and microwave radiometer (MWR) observations is presented in this study. It was demonstrated that LWC can be retrieved in real conditions with an uncertainty of less than 0.05 g/m^3 .

Main Illustration:

Legend: Scatterplot and corresponding statistics between the in-cloud liquid water content retrievals from the microwave radiometer and cloud radar synergy with respect to in-situ measurements from a cloud droplet probe.

3 VIRTUAL MOBILITY GRANT

Topic : Advanced aerosol vertical profiling in drylands: case study of an olive grove

Reference of the VMG: Juan Luis Guerrero Rascado: Advanced aerosol vertical profiling in drylands: case study of an olive grove:
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1OIY4CiLqZ0HMwLBQX381uXSvCTPo3zI1/view>

Main outcomes: The aim of this VMG was to assess the GRASP potentiality, using a unique database (due to its natural conditions) combining ceilometer/Sun-photometer, for deriving advanced aerosol optical/microphysical profiles (biogenic/non-biogenic), based on a new aerosol typing (to be established in this VM) over one of the drylands most frequent in the Mediterranean basin: olive groves

Main Illustration:

Legend: Time series of the AOD at 440, 475, 870 and 1020 nm and the Angström exponent calculated from the AOD between 440 and 870 nm, obtained from the Sun-photometer at the Guadiana-UGR station in the period January 14 to March 31

Topic : Synergy for volcano eruption detection and characterization.

Reference of the VMG: Vanda Cristina Pires Salgueiro: Synergy for volcano eruption detection and characterization, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IsUTzTgajUmO-aAf73moaxpBcTno0PtQ/view>

Main outcomes: Tajogaite volcanic plumes (a total of three events) characterization in terms of optical and microphysical properties using the GRASP algorithm and remote sensing data (satellite data for plume detection and lidar/ceilometer + sun photometer for aerosol properties retrievals) obtained at different sites distributed over the Iberian Peninsula. The work done in the VMG resulted in the following publication <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2023.113684> where all the results are discussed

Main Illustration:

Legend: Vertical profiles of the backscatter coefficient and total volume concentration obtained from the GRASP retrievals. The layers are highlighted by the shadow areas. VC_{layer} and β_{layer} are the layer mean values.

Topic : Assessing radiative properties of extreme pollen events observed by synergy remote sensors in South-Eastern Iberian Peninsula

Reference of the VMG: Maria J.Granados-Munoz, V. Salgueiro, J-L. Guerrero-Rascado, Assessing radiative properties of extreme pollen events observed by synergy remote sensors in South-Eastern Iberian Peninsula. DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.10977478](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10977478).

Main outcomes:

A long-term analysis of EPEs for *Olea* and Cupressaceae using remote sensors combined with surface measurements is presented for the first time. The used methodology allows for an automatic characterization of pollen optical, microphysical and radiative properties profiles. Results show a slight larger contribution of Cupressaceae for the ARE SW component and a slight larger contribution of *Olea* for the LW component, with similar vertical distributions.

Main Illustration:

Legend: Mean vertical profiles of ARE (2013-2021) for SW and LW spectral ranges and total (SW+LW) retrieved from libRadtran calculations for Olea and Cupressaceae EPEs. The profiles correspond to a solar zenith angle of 60°.

Topic : PARAFOG application and strategy.

Reference of the VMG: J-F. Ribaud: PARAFOG application and strategy.
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/13sWPf54DVsy5fyYfoascfl-T19HUFaCD/view>

Main outcomes: Deployment of the PARAFOG near-real-time decision tool to support nowcasting fog formation events in Bulgaria (Burgas airport) and Slovenia (Ljubljana). PARAFOG tool effectively anticipated fog formation risk, issuing alerts tens of minutes prior to fog onset. Alert levels corresponded well with local weather analysis. These promising findings suggest potential future collaborations and considerations for PARAFOG distribution, including the development of a unified user-friendly interface for the end-users.

Main Illustration:

Legend:

Time series presenting measurements and the corresponding retrieved alert level outputs from PARAFOG version 2 during a radiation fog formation on 19 January 2022 at Ljubljana (Slovenia). From top to bottom panels, i) temperature and relative humidity, ii) wind speed, iii) rainfall, iv) visibility, v) cloud fraction between 0-1000m (400-6000m) over the last 2h (1h), vi) ALC-attenuated backscatter between 400 and 6000m, vii) ALC-attenuated backscatter between 0 and 400 m, together with the

altitude of the maximum gradient (fuchsia points) and the aerosol hydration (gray contours), viii) alert levels retrieved from PFG2, and viiii) fog type and PFG2 status.

Topic : Infrared-Microwave synergy to improve low liquid water path retrievals in fog

Reference of the VMG: D. Gallucci: Infrared-Microwave synergy to improve low liquid water path retrievals in fog.

Main outcomes:

- A statistical regressive technique based on the synergy of 14 Microwave channels (22 - 58 GHz) and Infrared (10.5 μm) observations, for the retrieval of Liquid Water Path in fog condition from ground-based observations
- Improved retrieval of Low Liquid Water Path for a dataset of synthetic brightness temperatures obtained with radiative transfer models, using atmospheric profiles from the NWP model AROME

Main Illustration:

Train/test over LWP < 2 mm

	14MW	14MW-IR	14MW-IR-IR ²
rmse (g/m2)	20.47	19.05	19.11
correlation	0.99	0.99	0.99

Train/test over LWP < 0.1 mm

	14MW	14MW-IR	14MW-IR-IR ²
rmse (g/m2)	12.32	9.08	8.19
correlation	0.88	0.93	0.95

Legend:

Left panel: Brightness Temperature sensitivity as a function of Liquid Water Path (LWP) based on MonoRTM radiative transfer model simulations for Microwave channel (red) and InfraRed channel (blue). *Right panel:* Multivariate Statistical regression showing the impact due to the addition of a quadratic term in the infrared, which is significant (compared to the microwave configuration or linear infrared only) particularly in the case the retrieval is focused on the low LWP regime (LWP<0.1mm), providing an improvement of around 30% in the root mean square error (rms).